

Supplementary Figure S1. Screen of *DrosDel* deletions on Chromosome 2L for rescue of *Adar*^{5G1} viability. Ratio of *Adar*^{5G1} to *FM7 Bar* genotypes among male progeny in the presence of *DrosDel* deficiencies, or in their absence (*w*¹¹⁸ cross at the bottom) (expressed as a percentage). Progeny are obtained by crossing *Adar*^{5G1} / *FM7, Bar* virgin females to males to *w*¹¹⁸ males or males of *DrosDel*/*SM5, Cy* deficiency stocks.